

A Study an Attitude towards Child Abuse among Children in Orphanages

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2653

Impact Factor: 4.012

Citation:

Arockia Priscilla, M.
“A Study an Attitude
towards Child Abuse
among Children in
Orphanages.” *Shanlax
International Journal of
Education*, vol. 7,
no. S1, 2019, pp. 12–16.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2599749](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2599749)

Dr.M.Arockia Priscilla

Principal, Mangayarkarasi College of Education, Madurai

Introduction

In the stage of the human lifespan, childhood is the most curial period, the need of special care and protection from the parents and family members too in the overall development of children. The child is a gift of god. They are facing too many challenges that make her / his to be mentally strong, physically fit, normally supportive in this society. But when the child is turn in to orphan the life is totally changed. An orphanage is a place where children without parents are cared for and housed. If a child has no parents the child is considered an orphaned. Orphans are parentless. An orphanage is an institution that takes care of orphans. An orphanage will care for tiny babies and also older children without parents care for children instill they can be placed is homes and adopted. The term “orphan” is often a misnomer. Most children who have lost a mother or father still have a living parent or other family members who are willing to care for them. However, many children have been separated or are at risk of being separated from family care for a range of reasons. Globally, it is estimated that well over 2 million children are living orphanages.

Children living in orphanages are at greater risk for long – term negative impact on their social, emotional and cognitive development. This is especially true for children under three years of age and for children living in large institutions for long periods of time. While higher quality residential care (small numbers of children living “family – style” with consistent, well-trained caregivers) can help minimize these impacts, research shows that children growing up within families fare better in the long term than children raised in orphanages.

Some of the reason for orphage are listed below

1. Main reason children become orphaned at that their parents have died
2. Poverty
3. Non – biological care given
4. Stigma
5. Alcohol abused parents

6. Discrimination
7. Material neglect
8. School neglect
9. Child labor
10. Exploitation
11. Emotional abuse
12. Sexual abuse
13. Physical abuse

Physical maltreatment (or) sexual molestation of a child is called child abuse. Child abuse is when apparent or caregiver, whether through action or failing to act, causes injury, death, emotional harm, or risk of serious harm to a child.

Objective of the Study

1. To study the relationship between the child abuse and children in orphanage.
2. To find out the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of gender.
3. To find out the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of age.
4. To find out the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of kind of orphaned.
5. To find out the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of Educational qualification.
6. To find out the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of type of orphanage.

Hypotheses

1. There is no positive attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of gender.
3. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of age.
4. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of type of orphan.
5. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of educational qualification.
6. There is no significant difference in the attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages in terms of type of orphanage.

Terms and Definitions

Orphan: Orphans are parentless.

Orphanage: An orphanage is a place where children without parents are cared for and housed.

Child Abuse: Physical maltreatment (or) sexual molestation of a child is called child abuse. There are many forms of child maltreatment, including neglect, physical abuse, sexual abuse, exploitation and emotional abuse.

Delimitations and Scope of the Study

The finding of the study will reveals that the orphanage and child abuse is positively correlated because the absence of healthy atmosphere in orphanages. It cannot be over generalized and

considered as an overall reflection of orphan in other cities. However, it may give an idea about the orphanage and child abuse. This study identifies the female child is abused frequently. There are other variable which have not been taken in to account.

Planning of the Checklist Cum Rating Scale

The researcher studied the concept attitude towards child abuse among orphanage in details and decides the following 5 variables which are focused among the orphan after a pilot study conducted in this regard.

1. Gender
2. Age
3. Kind of orphaned
4. Educational qualification
5. Type of orphanage

Test and Retest Method

The test was administered to the 30 orphans and re administered among the same 30 after of 15days. The comparative performance and deviations were analyzed. The deviation is negligible Hence, the tool is assured to be having reliability. Thus, the reliability was ensuring the try out.

Establishing Validity of the Tool

The face & content validity was established for this tool. The face & content validity was checked with orphans. The concurrent validity was checked by repeated administration of the tool. According to Garret, H.E (1967, P.365), the index of reliability is also taken as a measure of validity.

Scoring

For the purpose of scoring, the score for check list were counted. For the rating scale, 3 marks were given to often , 2 marks were given to sometime and 1 mark was given never response.

Sample

The investigator has followed simple random sampling method for the present study. There were 30 orphans taken for the study. The investigator used percentage analysis for the study.

Significance of the Study

It is a common scene of orphan having negative attitude towards his/her family. Because the evidence demonstrates that children are more likely to be abused or neglected in institutional care, it is important to support the well – being and protection of children in all setting now a day the children are very easily abused through the negative usage of social media. In earlier day family used to take care of their children action in every minute. But in this fast and busy world the parents doesn't have a time to listen her/his child's emotional expression. Automatically the children are falling in the emotional abused relationship even in schools, neighborhood, friends, etc., Family is a first and best institution for a child to enrich her/his in emotionally, morally, socially, spiritually, and economically. This study just expresses the attitude of the orphan regarding the child abuse in this society. Hence this study focuses their attitude towards child abuse among the orphans are strongly supported because of the misbehavior in orphanages.

Analysis & Interpretation of data

Hypotheses: 1

There is positive attitudes towards child abuse among children in orphanages. The details regarding the correlations between orphan & child abuse are presented in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Percentage Analysis of attitude towards child abuse among children in orphanages

S.No.	Level	No.of Response	Percentage
1.	Low	4	13.3
2.	Moderate	17	56.6
3.	High	9	30

It is evident from the Table 1 that there is a moderate correlation between the orphan & child abuse.

Hypotheses: 2 There is no signification difference in the attitude of orphan towards child abuse in team of gender.

Table 2

S.No.	Gender	No.of Response	Percentage
1.	Male	9	30
2.	Female	21	70

It is evident from the table 2 that the obtained percentage is 30 for male. It is lesser then the female’s percentage. There is a difference in their attitude towards child abuse in terms of gender. Hence it is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses: 3 There is no signification difference in the attitude of orphan towards child abuse in team of Age.

Table 3

S.No.	Age	No. of Response	Percentage
1.	0 – 13	4	13.33
2.	13 – 19	12	40
3.	above 19	14	46.66

The above table 3 reveals that orphan at the age of above 19 are most abused the other two categories. Hence it is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypotheses: 4 There is no signification difference in the attitude of orphan towards child abuse in team of Kind of orphan.

S.No.	Kind of Orphan	No.of Response	Percentage
1.	Parents died	12	40
2.	Diseased – HIV/AIDS	5	16.7
3.	Corruption	6	20
4.	Poverty	5	16.7
5.	Difficulties in Adoption Process	2	6.7

It is evident from the table 4 that the percentage analysis shows that the orphans whose parents are died are more abused than other categories. Hence it is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis: 5 There is no signification difference in the attitude of orphan towards child abuse in team of Educational qualification.

S.No.	Educational Qualification	No.of Response	Percentage
1.	School	12	40
2.	Higher Education	18	60

It is evident from the table 5 that the percentage analysis shows that the orphan those who are all having higher education are more abused than school going orphans. Hence it is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis: 6 There is no signification difference in the attitude of orphan towards child abuse in team of type of orphanage.

S.No.	Type of Orphanage	No.of Response	Percentage
1	Government	2	6.66
2	Non- government	28	93.33

It is evident from the table 5 that the percentage analysis shows that the orphans those who are living in non-government organization are abused mostly than the government cell. Hence it is significant. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

Today in this complex world the orphan girls face innumerable problems identified by Anea the psychologies academic performance pressure, Body image, awareness & self – acceptance, confusion about direction and future, Dating (Choices, relationship, break –ups, sexual activity), divorce – related challenges, friendship dynamics (growing apart, betrayal, conflicts, negative (competitions), Goal setting, pursuit and low self – esteem, peer media & self imposed pressure, social solution, bullying, stress, Time Management, organization & life skills and Teen / Parents communication.

It may be concluded from the above findings that orphan girls at the age of above 19 are abused frequently because most of their parents are died. Hence no one will raise the question towards the abuse in the orphanages. The majority of the female, higher education children is abused in the private institution. Orphan itself because of their poverty and their back ground of their life style. Orphaned life can change a child, making at so that their transition in to traditional family until will entail a few bumps in the road. Understanding the life they once came from and inspect it may have on there is the first step in helping them overcome those difficulties.